

Investigating Different Options for Reheating the First Converter Inlet Stream of Sulfur Recovery Units (SRUs)

H. Ganji, H. R. Mahdipoor, J. Ahmadpanah, H. Naderi

Abstract—The modified Claus process is the major technology for the recovery of elemental sulfur from hydrogen sulfide. The chemical reactions that can occur in the reaction furnace are numerous and many byproducts such as carbon disulfide and carbon carbonyl sulfide are produced. These compounds can often contribute from 20 to 50% of the pollutants and therefore, should be hydrolyzed in the catalytic converter. The inlet temperature of the first catalytic reactor should be maintained over than 250 °C, to hydrolyze COS and CS₂. In this paper, the various configurations for the first converter reheating of sulfur recovery unit are investigated. As a result, the performance of each method is presented for a typical clause unit. The results show that the hot gas method seems to be better than the other methods.

Keywords—Sulfur recovery unit, reaction converter.

I. INTRODUCTION

MOST of the catalysts used for the treatment of hydrocarbons in the petrochemical industries are highly susceptible to poisoning by sulphur compounds. It is thus essential to separate hydrogen sulfide from feed stocks such as sour natural gases or crude oil [1]. The modified Claus process is the major technology for the recovery of elemental sulfur from H₂S and SO₂ [2]. All requirements to be met by Claus plants are dictated by the operating conditions of modern, flexible refineries and natural gas plants and increasingly stringent emission control regulations [3]. Therefore, Sulfur recovery units (SRUs) do not directly increase the net present value of the refinery and they are necessary to match all stringent environmental regulations [4].

The modified Claus process consists of a high temperature front-end reaction furnace, followed by catalytic reaction stages. This process continues to be the most widely used process for the conversion of H₂S to sulfur. Generally, Byproduct gases originating from physical and chemical gas and oil treatment units in refineries, natural gas processing and gasification plants are also routed to Claus unit [3]. The overall reaction characterizing the process is as follows [4],

H. Ganji is with the Research Institute of Petroleum Industry, Tehran, 14665-137 Iran (phone: +982148252120; fax: +982144739713; e-mail: ganjih@ripi.ir).

H. R. Mahdipoor is with the Research Institute of Petroleum Industry, Tehran, 14665-137 Iran (phone: +982148252520; fax: +982144739713; e-mail: mahdipoorhr@ripi.ir).

J. Ahmadpanah is with the Research Institute of Petroleum Industry, Tehran, 14665-137 Iran (phone: +982148253103; fax: +982144739713; e-mail: Ahmadpanahsj@ripi.ir).

H. Naderi is with the Research Institute of Petroleum Industry, Tehran, 14665-137 Iran (phone: +982148253103; fax: +982144739713; e-mail: naderiha@ripi.ir).

A key reaction that occurs in front-end reaction furnace is a two step sequence, 1/3 of the acid gas is oxidized to SO₂ using air,

This combustion generates a large amount of heat. Further, the combustion products undergo Claus reaction between H₂S and SO₂,

Reaction 3 is a reversible exothermic reaction. Thus, processing under adiabatic condition greatly increases temperature, which lowers equilibrium conversion to about 75%. Effluent gas from the reaction furnace passes through a waste heat boiler (WHB) to recover heat and produce high-pressure steam. Likewise, a large amount of elemental sulphur (S₂) are produced during of thermal decomposition H₂S. In fact, Elemental sulfur produced in the furnace is about 50-60% of the total sulfur production of the plant [5].

In the second step or catalytic reaction stages, the remained unreacted H₂S are reacted with SO₂, over an alumina catalyst to form elemental sulfur in fixed bed reactors. The reaction is the same as eq. 3 [1,6]. Since this reaction is exothermic, decreasing the temperature leads the equilibrium reaction toward right hand, i.e. more sulfur yields. On the other hand, low temperatures decrease the reaction rate. Therefore, an appropriate catalyst must be used to increase the reaction rate. However, high sulfur yields still necessitate a multistage process with interstage cooling and sulfur condensation [7]. Although the modified Claus process has remained relatively unaltered since its introduction, further modifications to the basic process have been introduced in order to increase the plant capacity or efficiency [8].

As mentioned before, the chemical reactions that can occur in the reaction furnace are numerous and many byproducts such as carbon disulfide (CS₂) and carbon carbonyl sulfide (COS) are produced. These compounds can often contribute from 20 to 50% of the pollutants in the tail-gas [9-12]. Furthermore, presence of O₂ traces in the CS₂ - H₂O mixture caused a decrease in the activity of alumina and titania catalysts due to sulfate formation [13]. Therefore, COS and CS₂ should be hydrolyzed in the catalytic converter [14,15], as shown below:

The temperature of the first catalytic reactor is maintained at about 350 °C to hydrolyze COS and CS₂, while that of the subsequent reactors is just above the sulfur vapor dew point

At second step, using hot gas will be studied. As mentioned at introduction, among available alternatives, the best configuration for reheating of first reactor inlet stream seems to be using hot gas (see figure 1, after WHB). Figure 3 represents the changes in the temperature of first converter inlet stream with changes in the hot gas split ratio. As is shown in this figure, the temperature of 250 °C which is an appropriate temperature for first converter inlet stream is achievable at hot gas split ratio equal to about 6.5 percent. Although using hot gas omits the cost of using high pressure steam, it can decrease overall sulfur recovery of unit. However, it can be compensated when tail gas treatment unit is applied after Claus sulfur recovery unit. More increase in the temperature of first converter inlet stream is possible by increasing the hot gas bypass ratio.

Fig. 3 The changes in temperature of first converter inlet stream vs. hot gas split ratio Figures

Finally, the use of inline burners will be investigated for reheating the process gas flowing to first converter. The inline burner burns a portion of acid gas feed to SRU or the fuel gas to produce a hot gas. Mixing this hot gas with outlet stream of WHB will increase the temperature of first converter inlet stream. This method omits the pressure drop of the heat exchanger in the first method and operability problems of second one, but decrease of overall sulfur recovery is present yet, because it insert the large amounts of inert gas to the process gas. Moreover, the cost of fuel gas will increase working capital investment. For this case study, using a fuel gas inline burner is supposed. Figure 4 show the increase in the temperature of first converter inlet stream with the increase of fuel gas (here we use natural gas) flow rate. As is shown in figure, 55 Kg/h is required to reach the temperature of first converter inlet stream above 250 °C.

Fig. 4 The changes in temperature of first converter inlet stream vs. mass flow rate of fuel gas inserting into the inline burner

III. CONCLUSIONS

The modified Claus process is the major technology for the recovery of elemental sulfur from hydrogen sulfide. The chemical reactions that can occur in the reaction furnace are numerous and many byproducts such as carbon disulfide and carbon carbonyl sulfide are produced. These compounds can often contribute from 20 to 50% of the pollutants and therefore, should be hydrolyzed in the catalytic converter. The inlet temperature of the first catalytic converter should be maintained over than 250 °C, to hydrolyze COS and CS₂. In this paper, the various configurations for the first converter reheating of sulfur recovery unit were investigated. The achieved results show that the performance of each method and it was shown that using hot gas seems to be better than the other methods, especially when COS and CS₂ are major problem in SRU.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was supported by grants from Research and development of National Iranian Gas Company.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. P. Elsner, M. Menge, C. Müller, D. W. Agar, "The Claus process: teaching an old dog new tricks", *Catalysis Today* 79–80, 2003, pp. 487-494.
- [2] J. S. Eow, "Recovery of Sulfur from Sour Acid Gas: A Review of the Technology", H. Fisher, *Burner/Fire box design improves sulfur recovery*, Hydrocarbon processing, 1974, pp. 27-30.
- [3] B. ZareNezhad, An investigation on the most important influencing parameters regarding the selection of the proper catalysts for Claus SRU converters, *J. Ind. Eng. Chem.* 15, 2009, pp. 143-147.
- [4] S. Signor, F. Manenti, M. G. Grottoli, P. Fabbri, and, S. Pierucci, *Sulfur Recovery Units: Adaptive Simulation and Model Validation on an Industrial Plant*, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 2010, 49, pp.5714-5724.
- [5] K. A. Hawboldt, W. D. Monnery, W. Y. Svrcek, "A Study on the Effect of Quench Design on the Quality of Experimental Data", *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 1999, 38 (6), pp. 2260-2263.
- [6] L. V. Nasato, K. Karan, A. K. Mehrotra, and, L. A. Behie, "Modeling Reaction Quench Times in the Waste Heat Boiler of a Claus Plant", *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 1994, 33, pp. 7-13.
- [7] N. I. Dowling, J. B. Hyne, and D. M. Brown, "Kinetics of the Reaction between Hydrogen and Sulfur under High-Temperature Claus Furnace Conditions", *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 1990, 29, pp. 2327-2332.

- [8] H. R Mahdipoor, R. Hayati, R. Khorsand, H Javaherizadeh, "Effect of Reaction Furnace and Converter Temperatures on Performance of Sulfur Recovery Units (SRUs), Journal of Petroleum Science Research, accepted to published, 2012.
- [9] G McIntyre, L. Lyddon, "Claus Sulphur Recovery Options", Bryan Research and Engineering, Inc. Technical Papers, Bryan, Texas.
- [10] H.M. Huisman, P. van der Berg, R. Mos, A.J. van Dillen, and J.W. Geus, "Hydrolysis of Carbon Sulfides on Titania and Alumina Catalysts: The Influence of Water", Applied Catalysis A, 115, 1994, pp. 157-172.
- [11] T.A. Gens, "Decrease in Carbonyl Sulfide in the Feed to Claus Converters by Shift Catalysts", Ind. Eng. Chem. Res. 33, 1994, pp. 1654-1656.
- [12] H.G. Paskall, "Reaction Furnace Chemistry and Operational Modes", Proceedings of Gas Sweetening and Sulphur Recovery Seminar, Comprimo/Western Research, Amsterdam (November, 1982).
- [13] Sames, J.A., Dale, P.R., Wong, B.: "Evaluation of Reaction Furnace Variables in Modified-Claus Plants" Proceedings of Lawrence Reid Gas Conditioning Conference, Norman, Oklahoma, (March, 1987).
- [14] E., I. Laperdrix, G Justin, O. Costentin, J.C. Saur, A. Lavalley, J.L. Aboulayt, and C. Nedez, "Comparative Study of CS₂ Hydrolysis Catalyzed by Alumina and Titania", Applied Catalysis B: Environment, 17, 1998, pp. 167-173.
- [15] D.M J. Puchyr, A.K Mehrotra, LA Behie, and N. Kalogerakis, "Hydrodynamic and Kinetic Modeling of Circulating Fluidized Bed Reactors Applied to a Modified Claus Plant", Chem. Eng. Sci. 51, 1996, pp. 5251-5262.
- [16] A.G. Maadah and R.N. Maddox, "Predict Claus Product", Hydrocarbon Processing 57, 1978, pp. 143-146.
- [17] R.A. Burns, R.B Lippert, and R.K. Kerr, "Choose Catalyst Objectively", Hydrocarbon Processing, 53, 1974, pp. 181-186.
- [18] Z.M. George, "Effect of Catalyst Basically for COS, SO₂ and COS Hydrolysis Reactions", J. catalysis, 35, 1974, pp. 218-224.
- [19] R.J.A.M. Terorde, P.J. van den Brink, L.M. Visser, A.J. van Dillen, and G.W. Geuss, "Selective Oxidation of Hydrogen Sulfide to Elemental Sulfur Using Iron Oxide Catalysts on Various Supports", Catalysis Today 17, 1993, pp. 217-224.
- [20] Gas Processors Suppliers Association (GPSA). Engineering Data Book; GPSA Tulsa, 1987; Chapter 22.